

FIBER OPTIC BEND SENSOR FOR IN-PROCESS MONITORING OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Wrinkles, porosity, delaminations and other defects introduced during the manufacturing processing can compromise mechanical performance of advanced composites. This paper describes a method of using fiber optic sensors for monitoring the formation of graphite fiber bending in real time. Theoretical formulation of the sensor behavior and experimental results are presented. The response of the sensor to composite fiber bending is characterized. The application to analyzing the formation of wrinkles in compression molding of graphite/epoxy composites is demonstrated.

1. Introduction

Matched-die compression molding is commonly used in fabricating advanced composites when high dimensional precision and surface finish requirements must be met. However, it can take much more effort to develop a compression molding process than an autoclave process. For compression molding the optimization of preform geometry, thermal cycles and mold closure is critical to the quality of the end product, and the control of these process parameters needs to be very precise.

Geometric features such as thick sections [1], large variation in cross-sectional thickness (i.e., high ply drop-offs), and high curvatures in composite parts are known to be difficult to process. In general, the interior and exterior of the material, due to low thermal through-thickness conductivity of the composite, are in different cure and viscosity states at any particular point in time. For parts with variable sectional thickness, a thicker section contacts the mold earlier than a thinner one due to the difference of bulk, which further exacerbates the differential pressure during the molding phase.

Fiber wrinkling or buckling is an important problem in manufacturing fiber-reinforced composites, because such defects can lead to degradation of mechanical performance [2,3]. Theoretical studies have been conducted to help understand the phenomenon of fiber wrinkling and buckling [4,5,6]. To deal with this manufacturing problem one needs to know when, how long, and under what conditions a wrinkle occurs. Although in-situ pressure, temperature, and dielectric sensors are commercially available for acquiring processing parameters, no specific equipment can clearly delineate in-process wrinkle formation. This requirement is beyond the capabilities of current non-destructive method such as conventional ultrasonic scanning or X-ray CT. These methods are effective at analyzing composites in the cured state but are constrained by the presence of mold and evolving nature of material states. Thus the development of a new wrinkle sensing technique is necessitated.

2. Sensing of Fiber Bending

Fiber optics were selected as the methodology for wrinkle sensing. In composites, graphite fibers initially aligned in parallel layers must go through a bending transformation to become wrinkles. Using fiber optics, the severity of bending can be identified and quantified based on the curvature and the total path of bending. The process can be measured by the light attenuation via optical fibers embedded in the composite. The highly sensitive fiber optic sensors can survive the typical processing environment of most polymer composite. Their small size, easy conformance to complex part geometry and immunity to EMI make them readily applicable to current state-of-the-art shop practices.

The system consists of a light-emitting and sensing unit with multiplexed ports to optical fibers. It is integrated with a data acquisition unit to monitor processing conditions such as temperature, pressure and dielectric cure sensors. The schematic diagram of the bend sensing device is shown in Fig. 1. The bend sensor was developed based on the Photonetics 1450HS model with 110/140/150 μm commercial multimode fibers. [7]. A glass capillary was used to protect the reflector at the end of the fiber. Back reflected light was attenuated twice in a wrinkle.

Fig. 1 Schematics of A Fiber-Optic Bend Sensing System.

The basic principle of bending sensors is illustrated in Fig. 2. The fiber is made of two concentric layers of silica core and cladding, each with a different refractive index. For straight fiber, the total internal reflection angle is small. However, as the light path bends, the incident angle can increase, and some of them can be refracted into the cladding due to the changes of incidence angle. As a result, certain amount of light is lost. The loss corresponding to different degrees of bending can be characterized with respect to the bend radius and the length of bending.

Fig. 2 A Fiber Optic Bend Sensor. Due to the bend, light loss increases with incident angle .

3 Light Attenuation Due to Fiber Bending

Experiments and computer simulations have been conducted for the attenuation of light intensity in an optical fiber for on-line monitoring of wrinkle formation in composite manufacturing. The simulation incorporates a semi-empirical model for light losses based on laboratory calibration data and a commercial beam propagation code.

The Experiments

A Photonetics fiber optics probe modified to include a fully-reflective tip was used in the laboratory tests. The step-index fiber used has a core (refractive index, diameter) of (1.486, 100 microns) and a cladding refractive index of 1.457 at a wavelength of 0.85 μm . Sets of experimental data were obtained using two general types of configurations.

For the first configuration, the fiber was wrapped around several rods of various radii (1.55 mm, 3.10 mm, 3.75 mm, 6.33 mm) and light losses were measured. These were constant curvature bends with the total curved length computed as $4n\pi r$, where n is the number of turns.

In another configuration, the fiber was wrapped around a series of 2.44 mm radius posts of a "LEGO" block to form zigzag bends that realistically simulate typical wrinkles in composite manufacture. The distance between the centers of two adjacent posts are 7.98 mm. The modeling is somewhat complicated by the fact that the fiber actually forms a series of circular arc sections where it contacts the posts, alternating with spline sections between the posts. As shown in Fig. 3, the losses along the low-curvature spline sections are negligible, however, their main effect is to reduce the total curved path length along the circular sections, especially for the shorter configurations.

Fig. 3 Spline Approximation of Fiber Bend Between Two Circular Posts. The magnitudes of vectors show the curvature along the bend path.

Beam Propagation Simulation

A commercial computer program (BPMCAD) for design of integrated optics and was used to model the experimental data described above. Although not well-suited for modeling non-paraxial multimode wave guides, it was useful for confirming the reasonableness of the data and for fixing the parameters of the empirical model described below.

To simulate non-paraxial bends, it was necessary to apply a separate "conformal mapping" routine that simulates a bend by transforming the refractive index distribution for a straight fiber. The refractive index thereby picks up a linear gradient along the direction of the bend radius. The transmission results were found to be fairly sensitive to the (unknown) width of the initial light distribution and so the value of this width was determined by a best-fit against the data. The fit of the beam propagation model to a portion of the data is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Experimental Data for Light Attenuation Along Bend Radius R . Solid curves represent best-fit semi-empirical model; curves marked "b" were calculated using beam propagation code.

The fits using the beam propagation model indicate reasonable agreement with the laboratory data over the bend curvature radii and path lengths of interest. In order to simulate wrinkle formation, and development it was found desirable to have a faster and more flexible way to model bending losses. For this, a simple semi-empirical model was used in which the relative light intensity I along a uniformly bent fiber of curvature radius R is given by:

$$I = n1 \cdot e^{-a k(R) L} + n2 \cdot e^{-b k(R) L}$$

$$k(R) = e^{-(cR + dR^2)}$$

$$n1 = 0.5 \quad n2 = 0.5 \quad a = 0.14 \quad b = 0.005 \quad c = 0.6 \quad d = 0.03$$

where L measures the round-trip path length along the curved fiber.

The form of expression for I as the sum of two exponential values accounts for both transient and steady-state loss along the fiber [8]. The exponential dependence of the attenuation coefficient $k[R]$ on a second-degree polynomial in the curvature generalizes the coefficient for single mode fibers to the multimode case. From Fig 4, it may be noted that attenuation is significant only for sharp bends that would be encountered in laminate wrinkles. A drop in light transmission is therefore a practically unambiguous signature of a wrinkle using a continuous-wave light.

Simulating Wrinkle Formation

A wrinkle in composite laminate can be approximated by constant curvature sections as shown in Fig. 5. Using the empirical model for attenuation losses described above, we modeled the time development of a typical wrinkle growing to a final radius of 3.4 mm (center ply). The resulting light intensity after forward and reflected passes through the wrinkle is shown in Fig. 5. The light loss is easily detectable even at early stages of wrinkle development and is also insensitive to the precise location of the fiber in the wrinkle.

Fig. 5 Fiber Optic Sensors for Simulated Wrinkles in Composite Laminates. Shown are the calculated intensities of a reflected pass through typical wrinkle at two stages of its development. Points marked "1" and "2" are at different plies through the wrinkle.

4. Application of Bend Sensor to Composite Processing

An experiment was conducted for an graphite/epoxy laminate that was difficult to mold due to its significant variation of thickness. The region of interest, as shown in Fig. 6, is 4 inches at the thickest section. The composite was a quasi-isotropic lay-up unidirectional prepreg.

Two primary loops of optical fibers were embedded in the composite at 32 plies below the top surface. Each loop had a 5 mil gold wire embedded parallel to it to enhance the x-ray CT image for verifying wrinkles existence. In addition, secondary loops were also installed at 2 plies below the primary loop as backup. Surrounding and inside the region of interest, fiber optic pressure sensors were also used to obtain pressure data and for calculating pressure gradients. In addition, thermocouples and dielectric cure sensors were used to record pressure and resin degree of cure at key locations. During the lay-up, channels were precisely cut on the ply for embedding the sensors to minimize the interference to actual processing conditions.

Fig. 6. An Experiment of In-Process Wrinkle Sensing. Thick laminates and complicated ply drop-off in a real-part were used. Gold wires were embedded adjacent to the optical fibers to enhance X-ray CT and to verify the existence of wrinkles.

The post manufacturing inspection using x-ray CT confirmed that there was a series of wrinkles formed in the shaded region in Fig 6. The sensor in *loop 2* did not survive handling and operations before molding. The wrinkle sensor reading in *loop 1*, as illustrated in Fig. 7, shows a distinct signature of intensity drop during wrinkle formation of a period that is less than one minute. Typical pressure profiles near the wrinkle region are shown in Fig 8. At the time of wrinkle inception, a sudden rise of pressure at the rate nearly 1000 psi/sec was observed.

Fig. 7 Light Signal Reading from a Bend Sensor. The distinct drop of reading indicates the formation of wrinkles.

Fig. 8. Sudden Rise and Decay of Pressure Zoomed-in At the Time of Wrinkle Formation.

Afterwards, the pressure quickly returned to normal indicating that the material has being relocated and the wrinkle was formed. This information suggests that process parameters can be fine tuned in a relative small time window to avoid wrinkles.

5. Concluding Remarks.

A practical method has been developed to sense the formation of fiber wrinkles in real time. The present work demonstrates that a commercially-available fiber optic sensor can be modified to provide a sensitive and unambiguous monitoring capability for typical wrinkle forming situations. The performance of the sensor in graphite/epoxy during compression molding processes of laminated composites was satisfactory. With low cost and easy implementation, the method can be useful in developing manufacturing processes for composite material.

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